

The behavior of agricultural innovation diffusion: Altmetric evidence

Jaehyun Ahn¹, Mathew Baker², Bruce Herbert³

¹jaehyun.ahn@ag.tamu.edu, ²mathew.baker@ag.tamu.edu, ³bruce.herbert@ag.tamu.edu
Texas A&M University, Dept. of Agricultural Leadership, Education and Communications
600 John Kimbrough Blvd., College Station, Texas 77543 (USA)

Abstract

Agricultural innovations continue to evolve as new challenges arise in our global food system. To diffuse and adopt innovations/inventions, we should consider actors who lead, follow, and connect in a network (Rossi et al., 2019). This research-in-progress paper highlights current innovations communicated electronically and monitored through Altmetric. We frame our findings using Rogers's (2003) diffusion of innovations theory. A social network map and a cross-correlation matrix show how countries are connected and the original words/phrases (or those closely related) regarding agricultural innovations. Over the last decade, Altmetric has collated scholarly content with hundreds of thousands of conversations and brings great potential encompassing various innovations, helping us understand the better societal interest in agricultural innovations and how such innovations diffuse and adopt globally.

Introduction

Farming and animal husbandry began with human civilization and advanced considerably in facing the challenges of evolution, societal changes, tacit knowledge, and scientific discovery. However, we see bifurcated results on a continuum anchored on one side by commercial agriculture challenged to feed the 9.7 billion world population by 2050 (Ahn et al., 2022; Roser et al., 2013) and others who work in regenerative agriculture more focused on sustainable production systems (Hobbs et al., 2008; Kassam et al., 2009). Conversely, Rosen (2013) delivers an archaeological viewpoint of agriculture's evolution of care for small companion animals. Once raising pets were pragmatic to protect harvested crops from grain-eating rodents and protecting livestock from predators. However, today, small animals serve as companions to humans and in many cases considered an extension of the family. In this research-in-progress paper we accommodate the breadth of agriculture and publications of agricultural innovations from 1982 to 2021 based on precise classifications of research topics.

Our substantive interest is addressed in three phases. Phase one connects one country to another through affiliation or market access to research on agricultural innovations. Then we search for terms and phrases across the literature in the second phase. Finally, these findings foreshadow our plans for a complete bibliometric-aided research project, which will continue these findings.

This research may complement or contradict the *Diffusion of Innovations* theory proposed by Rogers (2003) as time and additional cases are examined to provide insight to the drivers of innovations, their diffusion, and ultimate adoption. Rogers (2003) walks across various innovations/inventions across disciplines to demonstrate how a social system distributes information/ideas. Spontaneous or planned diffusion makes an individual or a group adopt or reject an innovation/invention. However, in most cases persuasion is necessary between the diffusion of innovations and its respective adoption/rejection, incorporating who, what, when, and how senders and receivers communicate about the attributes of an innovation including relative advantage, trialability, observability, complexity, and compatibility in the context of the adopters' system. The innovation-adoption process is dynamic and changes with the operation and belief of a social system (Rogers, 2003).

Like many who study innovations, we have relied upon the work of Rogers (2003) to inform our curricula in higher education and Extension, but a more granular inspection of communication channels and the diffusion of information across platforms and channels may provide cause us to challenge Rogers (2003). Several forces and factors, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, concerns about global warming, and new technologies such as CRISPR (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats), have resulted in new agendas and priorities. Globally, the United Nations (UN) shared the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015, promoting a concerted effort for all member countries, whether developing or developed, to embrace the 17 universal goals (Samarasinghe & Carver, 2017). Each goal is not mutually exclusive, and several publications in our data unite SDG 1: No Poverty, SDG 2: Zero Hunger, as well as SDG 5: Gender Equality. Alternatively, more publications caught our eyes that focused on SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, SDG 13: Climate Action, and SDG 15: Life on Land. Innovation research is more diverse, transdisciplinary, and unilaterally, bilaterally, or multilaterally focused.

In a narrow reality, nations and continents face various challenges – and innovations respond to those challenges and opportunities. A takeaway from current bibliometric-aided research is that the one-size-fits-all reason is no longer valid for devising, diffusing, and adopting innovations. Our research will inform the Rogers's (2003) Model as we explore social media's influence on the diffusion of innovations and use innovative analysis techniques to gain a deeper understanding of worldwide agricultural innovations.

Data

Altmetric monitors the number of conversations (Who's talking about your research? n.d.) about research, both positive and negative. It is a measure of social engagement with scientific research. The publisher tracks hundreds of thousands of exchanges about scholastic findings and implications in 19 communication sources – social network services, mass media, Wikipedia, citations, and more. Through the Altmetric Explorer database at Texas A&M University Libraries, we organized 2,752 publications in eight subject fields:

Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences, Biological Sciences, Chemical Sciences, Earth Sciences, Engineering, Environmental Sciences, Psychology and Cognitive Sciences, and Technology.

Altmetric Attention Score

The publisher assigns an Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) and represents those conversations. A rule of thumb is a proportionate relationship between mentions and AAS. However, more citations than mentions do not necessarily conjugate higher AAS for social impact. The score helps identify the attention of our society and the content we care about (What are Altmetrics? n.d.).

Progress

We identified and sampled 600 publications in an Excel spreadsheet out of the publications described in the Data section, i.e., about 22%. Our spreadsheet includes information on the abstract, keyword(s), and the UN-used alpha-3 code/three-letter country code to which the researcher is affiliated and researched. This sample included 91 countries. Additional information on labor productivity (in agriculture, forestry, and fishing), value added per worker (constant 2015 US\$), GHG Emissions and Energy Use (GHG) in metric tons, and electric power consumption in kWh per capita (Electricity) from the World Bank were included in our dataset. We screened the publications and updated highlights in addition to the abstract. The count ranged from 280 to 782 words per publication, and about 289,200 words were processed.

We used three software programs to analyze our data. Stata (v.17 standard edition) was for data mining, summary statistics, and data type conversion to the final Excel spreadsheet. For example, we merge the World Bank information into the existing Altmetric spreadsheet by Stata. In Table 1 we included summary statistics of key variables associated with individual publications and country of origin. Commonly, each variable indicates that the distribution hovers skewed. Against the AAS mean of 12, only four publications record more than 200 which primarily discussed *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) corn, cotton, and Genetically Modified (GM) canola (Biden et al., 2018; Dively et al., 2018; Heinemann et al., 2014; Lu et al., 2012). For economic indicators, high standard deviations imply a significant gap between developing and developed countries. However, low correlations existed between AAS with the economic indicators, i.e., $r(\text{AAS-labor productivity}) = .14$, $r(\text{AAS-GHG}) = .15$, and $r(\text{AAS-electricity}) = .17$.

Stata was once again used for the network analysis with the Pajek program. Pajek's Kamada-Kawai energy-based algorithm optimizes a network layout by eigenvectors. In a 2-D graph layout comprising edges directing vertices in blue/red colored representing different edge crossings, we understood how the first authors' affiliated country researched another or their own country (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998). Stata complemented essential information of the network.

Last, we imported the Stata-processed Excel spreadsheet to VantagePoint (v.14). The software refined quantitative information and processed bibliometric-aided analysis.

Table 1. Summary statistics

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Observations</i>	<i>Min.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Max.</i>	<i>SD</i>
AAS	600	0	12	653	40
Labor Productivity	599	235	45,959	110,633	37,410
GHG	598	.2	9	19	6
Electricity	570	39	6,761	23,000	4,671

Note: labor productivity in constant 2015 US\$, GHG emissions and energy use in metric tons, and electric consumption in kWh per capita

Results

Figure 1 displays the Kamada-Kawai layout between countries affiliated-researched, containing 91 nodes/vertices, 112 arcs, 4,032 paths, and a sparse density/network (<.02). The diameter is eight, and the average shortest path is 3.2. The interconnectivity of agricultural innovations appears denser between nodes in red than others connected in green. Near the clockwise end, Iran (IRN), Peru (PER), the Philippines (PHL), Hungary (HUR), Romania (ROU), Thailand (THA), Azerbaijan (AZE), Sudan (SDN), Russia (RUS), and Latvia (LVA) remain isolated with no edges/links.

However, the countries in the center form a dense network. The United States (USA) neighbors Australia (AUS), Brazil (BRA), Canada (CAN), China (CHN), Ethiopia (ETH), Ghana (GHA), Kenya (KEN), Nigeria (NGA), and Uganda (UGA). The nine neighbors stretch out zero to eight countries, respectively. For example, Australia (AUS) links to not only the United States (USA) but the United Kingdom (GBR), Bangladesh (BGD), Kenya (KEN), Cambodia (KHM), Sweden (SWE), New Zealand (NZL), and Nigeria (NGA). But Nigeria (NGA) makes no connection with others.

The Netherlands (NLD) connects more than the United States (USA). The Dutch network expands the USA as well as other European countries (i.e., France (FRA), Germany (DEU), Spain (ESP)), African countries (i.e., Ethiopia (ETH), Ghana (GHA), Kenya (KEN), Uganda (UGA)), South America (i.e., Brazil (BRA), Uruguay (UGA)), Asia-Pacific countries (i.e., Cambodia (KHM), China (CHN), India (IND), Nepal (NPL), New Zealand (NZL)). The United States (USA) and the Netherlands (NLD) are two agricultural innovation hubs.

Centrality is vital to know how well all 91 countries are connected. Outdegree centrality (.15) is more than indegree (.1) centrality, which means more outgoing ties than incoming ties (Grund, 2015).

Besides mutual (edges on both countries), asymmetric (one edge from one country to another), and null dyads (isolation), we are interested in triads as well. The most apparent display is Bulgaria (BGR)-South Africa (ZAF)-Zimbabwe (ZWE)-Malawi (MWI). Using Stata, we find 40 complete. The transitivity coefficient (.56) shows, on average, that the chance that two countries share an agricultural innovation with another country is more than half.

Figure 1. Kamada-Kawai layout

Table 2 indicates that certain words and their closeness often emerged in agricultural innovations. Crossed with AAS, “behavior” often emerges with “center.” We interpret this match in a way that people, researchers, and policymakers communicate behavior-induced/behavior-centered innovations across eight subject fields. The verb “characterize” also aligns with “behavior” in “favor” of (= in support of) the proposed innovation. “Expertise” is another go-to word for “behavior” and “center” that convinces a particular agricultural innovation. We processed many volumes of basic science research/bench science research. “Gram” is frequent, and this basic unit in the metric system pairs well with “analysis” and “exercise,” in addition to “behavior” and “center.” The word “labor” happens fewer than “gram” and couples well with “favor.” Labor-favored/labor-saving technologies are ones we

have repeatedly heard of and seen. However, neither “supervising” nor “utilization” matches the words.

Table 2. Cross-correlation matrix

Records	crosswords	behavior	center	gram	analyzed	expertize	favor	analyzing	exercize	labor	characterize
44	behavior	1	0.892	0.807	0.782	0.838	0.838	0.775	0.761	0.646	0.655
30	center	0.892	1	0.93	0.915	0.845	0.903	0.764	0.832	0.785	0.549
25	gram	0.807	0.93	1	0.939	0.838	0.908	0.717	0.889	0.797	0.561
24	analyzed	0.782	0.915	0.939	1	0.775	0.933	0.69	0.898	0.799	0.58
21	expertize	0.838	0.845	0.838	0.775	1	0.795	0.701	0.764	0.688	0.554
19	favor	0.838	0.903	0.908	0.933	0.795	1	0.765	0.887	0.836	0.685
15	analyzing	0.775	0.764	0.717	0.69	0.701	0.765	1	0.727	0.746	0.669
12	exercize	0.761	0.832	0.889	0.898	0.764	0.887	0.727	1	0.772	0.717
10	labor	0.646	0.785	0.797	0.799	0.688	0.836	0.746	0.772	1	0.516
8	characterize	0.655	0.549	0.561	0.58	0.554	0.685	0.669	0.717	0.516	1

Note: Results from VantagePoint (v.14). Words cross-correlated with AAS. Values between 0 and 1.

Conclusions and future works

Our results contribute to how countries lead, follow, and connect in AAS as of our attention in agricultural innovations. We present social network analysis and list crosswords that publications with higher AAS use and correlate with each other. Science embraces various innovations from bench to commercial agriculture. We now have a deeper understanding of 600 publications across attributes of innovations, and the findings seem complementary to Rogers's (2003) framework.

As for Altmetric applications, our research topic – agricultural innovations – is well-targeted—hundreds of thousands of online communications about innovation research up and down daily. We reasonably capture attentive innovations around the world. However, we need more cases to incorporate and generalize our findings. Our priority is to add 2,152 publications in Phase Three of this innovation study.

More innovation cases may lead to more countries connected in a more extensive network and an updated cross-correlation map. We will strive to discover correlations between economic indicators and attentive innovations. We aim to generalize our findings further and specify that country-specific, continent-specific agricultural innovations encompass social, cultural, economic, and more relational attributes to a whole social network.

We conclude with an excerpt to remind our readers of our motivations for this study:

“We do not need more-of-the-same diffusion research. The challenge for diffusion scholars of the future is to move beyond the proven methods and models of the past, recognize their shortcomings and limitations, and broaden their conceptions of the diffusion of innovations (Rogers, 2003, p.xxi).”

References

- Ahn, J., Briers, G., Baker, M., Price, E., Strong, R., Piña, M., ... & Lu, P. (2022). Radio Communications on Family Planning: Case of West Africa. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(8), 4577. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19084577>
- Batagelj, V., & Mrvar, A. (1998). Pajek-program for large network analysis. *Connections*, 21(2), 47-57.
- Biden, S., Smyth, S. J., & Hudson, D. (2018). The economic and environmental cost of delayed GM crop adoption: The case of Australia's GM canola moratorium. *GM Crops & Food*, 9(1), 13-20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21645698.2018.1429876>
- Dively, G. P., Venugopal, P. D., Bean, D., Whalen, J., Holmstrom, K., Kuhar, T. P., ... & Hutchison, W. D. (2018). Regional pest suppression associated with widespread Bt maize adoption benefits vegetable growers. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(13), 3320-3325. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1720692115>
- Grund, T. (2015). Social network analysis using Stata. *Proceedings of Stata Users' Group Meetings, United Kingdom*, 21, Stata Users Group.
- Heinemann, J. A., Massaro, M., Coray, D. S., Agapito-Tenfen, S. Z., & Wen, J. D. (2014). Sustainability and innovation in staple crop production in the US Midwest. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 12(1), 71-88. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2013.806408>
- Hobbs, P. R., Sayre, K., & Gupta, R. (2008). The role of conservation agriculture in sustainable agriculture. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 363(1491), 543-555. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2007.2169>
- Kassam, A., Friedrich, T., Shaxson, F., & Pretty, J. (2009). The spread of conservation agriculture: justification, sustainability and uptake. *International journal of agricultural sustainability*, 7(4), 292-320. <https://doi.org/10.3763/ijas.2009.0477>
- Lu, Y., Wu, K., Jiang, Y., Guo, Y., & Desneux, N. (2012). Widespread adoption of Bt cotton and insecticide decrease promotes biocontrol services. *Nature*, 487(7407), 362-365. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature11153>
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Rosen, R. J. (2013, December 16). How humans created cats. *The Atlantic*. <https://theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2013/12/how-humans-created-cats/282391>
- Roser, M., Ritchie, H., Ortiz-Ospina, E., & Rodés-Guirao, L. (2013). World population growth. *Our World in Data*. <https://ourworldindata.org/world-population-growth>
- Rossi, P. H., Lipsey, M. W., & Henry, G. T. (2019). *Evaluation: A systematic approach* (8th ed.). Sage publications.
- Samarasinghe, N., & Carver, F. (2017). *Sustainable Development Goals: From promise to practice*. The United Nations Association – UK.
- What are Altmetrics? (n.d.). *Altmetrics*. Retrieved from November 20, 2022, from <https://altmetric.com/about-altmetrics/what-are-altmetrics/>
- Who's talking about your research? (n.d.). *Altmetrics*. Retrieved from November 20, 2022, from <https://altmetric.com>